

Implementation of Collaborative Learning Strategies in the Science and Social Studies Subject for Third Grade Students at SDN 1 Silanca

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the application of collaborative learning strategies in Natural and Social Sciences (IPAS) for third grade students at Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca. Using a qualitative descriptive approach, data was collected through observation, interviews, and documentation involving teachers and students as informants. The research findings reveal that collaborative learning improves students' engagement, understanding, and social interaction. Teachers play an important role as facilitators by designing heterogeneous groups of students, managing class dynamics, and providing guidance and feedback. The results showed that students showed increased critical thinking, active participation, mutual respect, and responsibility in group activities. Collaborative strategies also support contextual and meaningful learning, in line with the characteristics of elementary school students and the goals of the Independent Curriculum. Despite some challenges such as time constraints and uneven group participation, this strategy has proven effective in fostering an inclusive and dynamic learning environment. This study concludes that the systematic application of collaborative learning contributes significantly to the quality of science education and student development in the primary school environment.

KEYWORDS: Collaborative learning, science, basic education, group work, student participation.

INTRODUCTION

Education is very important because it helps people learn their abilities and how to use them to overcome challenges in life. A good education can help students become better at thinking, solving problems, and being creative, all of which are essential skills for success in life. (Farida et al., 2023) Education is a strategic means to improve the abilities and potential of human resources in order to be able to make the nation's children able to take part in the current global era. Education is a fundamental aspect in the development of quality human resources, where in the context of basic education, Natural and Social Sciences (IPAS) learning has a strategic role in shaping students' understanding of natural and social phenomena around them. One of the effective learning strategies is the collaborative strategy because collaborative learning is considered to provide opportunities to achieve success in teaching practice. Collaborative learning involves actively engaging learners and reducing differences between individuals. Collaborative learning is considered appropriate to be applied in the education system in Indonesia because it is in accordance with the culture of the Indonesian nation which upholds the value of cooperation. Collaborative learning is a situation where two or more people learn or try to understand something together. In contrast to individual learning, people involved in collaborative learning make use of each other's resources and skills (asking each other for information, assessing each other's ideas, supervising each other's work, etc.), (Muslimin et al., 2024) In the field of education, this tactic is applied through small group learning, where students interact with each other to develop a deep understanding. This approach is based on social learning theory and constructivism, which emphasizes that knowledge is acquired through interaction and collaboration. Important aspects of a collaborative strategy include building a shared vision and mission, building an inclusive work team, and developing a realistic and detailed work plan.

Social studies learning at the elementary school level is an important foundation for the development of students' science and social literacy in the future. In its implementation, science learning in elementary school is an integration of science and social studies subjects which aims to develop students' competencies in understanding natural and social phenomena holistically. The characteristics of science learning in elementary schools include contextual learning that relates the material to daily life, the development of science process skills and social inquiry, the use of the environment as a learning resource, and an emphasis on

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hands-on experience. (Ummah & Mustika, 2024). Social studies learning at the elementary level does encourage children's natural curiosity. Social studies learning also encourages children's curiosity because the material taught is related to the environment around students. In the context of IPAS learning strategies, learning design needs to accommodate the learning needs of elementary school students who still need concrete experience.

Agnafia et al. (2023) emphasize that an effective IPAS learning strategy should provide opportunities for exploration and discovery, encourage social interaction and communication, develop critical thinking skills, and facilitate experiential learning. Choosing the right learning strategy is the key to the success of achieving the learning objectives of IPAS, considering the characteristics of elementary school students who still need help and guidance in their learning process. The chosen learning strategy must be able to accommodate various learning styles of students and provide space for them to develop their potential optimally. Currently, various studies have shown that student-centered learning strategies are more effective in achieving learning goals compared to traditional teacher-centered approaches. The increasingly dynamic development of the world of education requires innovation in the learning strategy of IPAS in elementary schools. No matter how good the learning strategy is, it will certainly not be useful if it is not implemented well by the teacher. The role of teachers is irreplaceable in the implementation of this strategy. Teachers must be able to implement learning strategies well in order to achieve satisfactory learning outcomes. (Sanjani, 2021) This is a challenge in learning social studies at the elementary school level, considering the cognitive characteristics of students who are still in the concrete operational stage. Therefore, a learning strategy is needed that not only facilitates the understanding of concepts, but also encourages the development of critical thinking skills, creativity, and problem-solving skills. In this context, collaborative learning has emerged as one of the promising strategies to achieve these goals. Collaborative learning, as stated by Afriadi (2024) is a learning strategy that involves students working together in small groups to achieve common goals. This approach not only facilitates knowledge transfer, but also develops social and emotional skills that are essential for student development. Characteristics of collaborative learning that are in line with social science learning include positive interdependence between group members, face-to-face promotive interactions, individual and group responsibility, interpersonal and small group skills, and group processing.

The results of observations made by researchers at Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca revealed a number of challenges in the implementation of IPAS learning. The teaching and learning process is still dominated by lecture methods and teacher-centered approaches, thus limiting students' active participation. The lack of use of innovative learning strategies and the low ability of students to think critically and collaboratively are indications of the need for a change in pedagogical approaches that are more contextual and meaningful. Research on the implementation of collaborative learning strategies in science subjects in grade three of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca has theoretical and practical significance. Theoretically, this study aims to develop a contextual concept of social studies learning strategies, enrich academic references on collaborative strategies, and test the application of constructivist learning theory in the context of basic education. Practically, this research is expected to provide alternative effective learning strategies, improve the quality of the IPAS teaching and learning process, develop teachers' competence in designing innovative learning, and facilitate the development of students' potential comprehensively. Based on the above background, the main solution that can be applied is the application of a structured collaborative model by forming small groups consisting of 3-4 students with diverse abilities. In its implementation, it is necessary to design assignments that encourage positive interdependence between members and a role rotation system to ensure the active participation of all students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Collaborative learning has become one of the most effective learning strategies in the modern world of education. According to (Suryani, 2016) collaborative learning is a learning philosophy that facilitates students to work together, support each other, learn and grow together, and develop collectively. In effective collaborative learning, the success of the group depends on the individual learning of all group members. Students are responsible for ensuring that all group members understand the material and can complete the assigned assignments.

Provide an in-depth perspective on the nature of collaborative learning by emphasizing the importance of meaningful interaction between students. According to him, collaborative learning is not only about grouping students, but about how to create a situation where two or more individuals can be actively involved in a mutually beneficial learning process. These interactions cover various aspects of learning, from conceptual discussions to joint problem-solving, all of which contribute to the formation of a deeper understanding of the learning material. Students can do assignments, according to their respective experiences even though their experience is still little compared to other members, as long as they are able to think clearly and well according to their capacity.

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The essence of learning Natural Sciences and Social Sciences (IPAS) in the context of the Independent Curriculum in Elementary Schools is a comprehensive integration between science learning and social phenomena that aims to develop students' ability to understand the surrounding world holistically. Wulandari et al. (2021) Science learning in the Independent Curriculum emphasizes the development of students' competencies in analyzing the reciprocal relationship between natural and social phenomena in daily life. This learning approach is in line with contextual learning principles that allow students to build a meaningful understanding of the world around them. Adawiyah and Jennah (2023) explained that IPAS learning in the Independent Curriculum is designed to develop science literacy and social literacy in an integrated manner. Learning is no longer fixated on a rigid division of subjects, but rather presents a learning experience that relates natural phenomena to the socio-cultural context of the community. This is reinforced by research conducted by Nikmah et al. (2024) which shows that an integrated approach in social studies learning can improve students' critical thinking skills and understanding of the relationship between scientific and social aspects in daily life. The application of IPAS learning in the Independent Curriculum, according to (Pramesti et al., 2023), emphasizes the development of Pancasila student profiles through six main dimensions: faith and piety to God Almighty, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical reasoning, and creativity. In line with that, (Nikmah et al., 2024) emphasized that IPAS learning must provide space for students to develop 21st century skills, such as the ability to communicate, collaborate, think critically, and creatively. The assessment aspect in the learning of the Independent Curriculum IPAS as explained by Marisa and Ramadan (2024) uses a formative assessment approach that focuses on the learning process, not just the results. The assessment includes dimensions of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that are integrated in various learning activities. (Wijayanti and Ekantini (2023), added that social studies learning also needs to pay attention to the diversity of local contexts and local wisdom as a meaningful learning resource for students.

Socially, third-graders begin to show better ability to cooperate and interact with their peers. They are better able to work in groups and contribute to class discussions. Swihadayani (2023) Social skills and assistance will be able to create an atmosphere where students' feelings become more valuable and feel more useful, so that at this stage students will prefer collaborative learning. At this stage, students in the lower class have also shown their identities such as gender, friends, sharing, independence, and being able to compete with peers. Therefore, collaborative learning strategies are very suitable to be applied to science subjects in grade three . Collaborative learning allows students to actively participate, share ideas, and learn from each other, which can ultimately improve their understanding of the subject matter.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive type of research. The qualitative approach was chosen because this study aims to understand in depth the phenomenon of collaborative learning strategies in science subjects in grade three of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca. According to Sugiyono (2018), qualitative research is a method based on philosophy and is used to investigate the scientific circumstances (experiments) where researchers function as instruments, data collection techniques, and qualitative analysis that focus more on meaning. This type of descriptive research is used to systematically describe the facts and characteristics of the object or subject being researched precisely. This research will describe in detail how collaborative learning strategies are implemented, the challenges faced, and their impact on the science learning process.

The place of this research was carried out at Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca class three which is located in Silanca Village, Poso Regency, Central Sulawesi Province. This research was carried out on Friday, April 25 for the even semester 2024/2025. The researcher first gave permission to the school to conduct research for the process of taking and collecting research data. The subjects of this study are grade three students of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca with a total of 5 male students and 9 female students, so that the total number of students is 14 people.

Data collection techniques are the main step in research, because the main purpose of research is to obtain information. Without a data collection method, it is impossible for researchers to obtain data to achieve the information standards that have been set. Data collection is carried out through the arrangement, source, and collection method that is carried out through a natural setting. In this study, several data collection techniques were used as follows: Observation, this technique is carried out directly in the field by observing the process of teaching and learning activities carried out by teachers in the classroom using observation sheets at Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca. Interviews, this technique is done to collect data by conveying statements to students and recording or recording their answers. This data is used to find out their responses to the learning activities that have been carried out by teachers. Therefore, it is hoped that with the interview, the researcher can get answers from informants that are in accordance with the research objectives. The researcher used this method to obtain information on how to apply collaborative learning strategies in science subjects in grade three of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca.

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Documentation, this technique is carried out to collect data on student learning outcomes, learning processes, teacher data and documentation photos during research at Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca.

The data analysis used is qualitative and deductive, where an analysis is based on information obtained in the field at the time of the research. Furthermore, the information is processed into a pattern of relationships or hypotheses. From the hypothesis compiled based on the data, then the data that is processed repeatedly produces a conclusion from Sugiono (2016:335), namely through several processes, including: Data Reduction, data reduction is the slightening, classification, and disposal of data that is not needed in such a way that the data can produce meaningful informants and facilitate the drawing of conclusions. Data Presentation, at the data presentation stage, the researcher compiles a structured description of information to draw conclusions and take action. The data presented uses the form of narrative text. Conclusion Drawn, the researcher draws conclusions and verifies by exploring the meaning of each symptom obtained and drawing conclusions from the data that has been concluded first, then matched with the notes and observations that have been made by the researcher during the research activities.

RESULT

Results of Interviews and Observations in Class three of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca

Based on the results of interviews conducted on April 25, 2025 with grade three teachers and two students as the main informants to obtain an overview of the implementation of collaborative learning in the IPAS learning process. Based on data obtained from an interview with the third-grade homeroom teacher of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca who stated that regarding the strategies used, the third-grade homeroom teacher explained that in learning the strategies used are diverse, for example, activity-based that involves all students directly in the learning process, project-based, technology-based, cooperation-based, and game-based. In response to this, the researcher conducted further interviews related to strategies in motivating students to actively participate in groups, the third-grade homeroom teacher gave his response that the role of teachers is very important, especially in helping students achieve learning goals, especially through group work and also guide, direct students, and provide resources and materials that support a discussion in group work. In order for the discussion process in the group to run smoothly, teachers must supervise and assess students in the group directly, and also provide feedback to improve the quality of group work.

Then the interview continued again about the role of the teacher as a facilitator to achieve the learning goals in the group, the third-grade homeroom teacher explained that in understanding how active participation in the group, in the formation of the group the teacher must choose how in a group there are students who can quickly grasp a learning so that everyone is actively involved. From the results of the interview above, it can be concluded that the learning strategies applied are collaborative and combine various methods to actively engage students. Teachers play the role of facilitators by guiding, directing and providing learning resources that support group work. In addition, teachers selectively form groups so that each member can participate optimally, while still monitoring and providing feedback to improve the quality of learning and student cooperation skills, so that the learning process becomes more effective and meaningful.

Based on data obtained from interviews with third grade students of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca regarding opinions or ideas during group work, one of the students said that the student was active in expressing his opinions and ideas during group work. Then the interview continued with the question of how usually students exchange opinions with their group mates, students said that they usually exchange opinions with their group mates, listen to each other and sometimes also ask if there is something that is not clear so that everyone can understand. The interview continued related to how students felt when working in a group, one of the students said that he felt happy and more excited when working in a group, the reason was because during group work, he could learn with friends, exchange ideas, and help each other if there was something that was not understood.

In response to this, the researcher asked again about how the students react when a friend puts forward an idea that differs from his opinion, one of the students said that he usually listens to the other friend if they have a difference of opinion. For example, if you disagree with the friend's opinion, they will discuss to find a solution together. From the results of the student interviews above, it can be concluded that students are active and enthusiastic in group learning. They find it easier to ask questions and discuss with friends, and enjoy learning together. Students also show an open attitude to different opinions and are able to interact well in groups. Overall, collaborative learning provides a pleasant learning experience and aids with material understanding.

Based on the results of research that has been conducted at Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca using interview, observation, and documentation techniques. The researcher presented the data from observations with informants related to the application of collaborative learning strategies in the science subjects of third grade students of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca. The informants related to this research are grade Three teachers and grade three students of Public Elementary Schools

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1 Silanca, As for the stages of the learning process given by grade three teachers which I can describe as follows, at the beginning of the third class homeroom teacher activity began with greetings and prayers as an opening, then invited students to sing the national anthem Indonesia Raya to instill a sense of love for the homeland as well as introduce the importance of preserving noble culture and mutual respect between cultures. Furthermore, teachers provide motivation to learn by relating the benefits of the material to be learned in daily life, as well as asking questions that connect previous knowledge with new material so that students are better prepared to receive learning. The teacher also explains the learning objectives and the scope of the material to be studied so that students understand the direction of learning activities.

In the core activity, students are directed to prepare their stationery on the table, then the teacher directs the students to open the theme book, after which the teacher delivers the learning material. The teacher provides the opportunity to ask and answer questions to deepen understanding, then the teacher gives assignments to students to be done in groups so that the learning process becomes interactive and supports better understanding. The teacher also encourages students to seek additional information from various sources independently in their respective groups. After the learning process, students are invited to evaluate the learning process that has been undertaken, at this stage students also explain the results of the discussion, while the teacher observes and provides comments and suggestions to enrich understanding.

The learning activity ended with a joint conclusion between the teacher and the educator regarding the important points of the material that had been studied. Students are given the opportunity to ask questions about things that are still not understood, or teachers give trigger questions related to the material as reinforcement and preparation for further learning. With this systematic series of activities, the learning process runs effectively and thoroughly, helping students understand the material about the hierarchy of local government in depth and contextual.

Based on the results of observations made during the IPAS learning process in grade three of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca in accordance with the indicators in the appendix, it can be seen that the aspect of student cooperation shows positive development in accordance with the indicators that have been set. First, in the interaction aspect, students actively discuss in groups and express their opinions with each other using polite language. This is in accordance with the indicators of participation in discussions, communication between group members, and the use of good and polite language. In addition, students also show an open attitude to new ideas which is an important indicator in creating a dynamic and inclusive learning atmosphere. Furthermore, in the aspect of cooperation, the assignment in groups is carried out fairly and equitably, and students support each other in completing tasks together. All group members actively participate and are able to complete tasks on time which shows the effectiveness of group cooperation. Students' ability to resolve conflicts well is also an indicator of success in building harmonious cooperation.

The aspect of social skills can also be seen from the ability of students to show empathy for friends, listen well to the opinions of others, and collaborate to solve problems together. This strengthens social relationships between students and supports the creation of a supportive learning environment. In the aspect of learning independence, students show high initiative to learn on their own and take responsibility for the tasks given. This indicator shows that students are not only dependent on the teacher's direction, but are also able to manage their learning process independently. Finally, in the aspect of reflection, students actively discuss the results of group work, provide feedback, plan improvement steps, but there are students who, if criticized by friends, have not received well so that they still need guidance from teachers to improve themselves in group learning.

Overall, it can be concluded that the learning process is systematically designed so that students are able to understand the material gradually and deeply. By incorporating collaborative learning strategies, this process not only emphasizes individual mastery of the material, but also encourages interaction, discussion, and collaboration between students in groups. This approach is effective in social studies learning because it is able to develop critical thinking, communication, and social responsibility skills, while increasing learning motivation and overall concept understanding. Thus, the implementation of systematic and collaborative learning measures creates an active, participatory, and contextual learning environment, which greatly supports the achievement of learning goals optimally and sustainably.

DISCUSSION

This study aims to determine the implementation of collaborative learning in the science subject of third grade students of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca. The data in this study was obtained from interviews and observations. When conducting interviews with teachers and students, the author found a difference with what happened during observation. Based on the interview results, the learning strategies applied are collaborative and combine various methods to actively engage students. Students are active and enthusiastic in group learning. They find it easier to ask questions and discuss with friends, and enjoy learning together. During the learning process, the author sees that the learning process runs effectively with active collaborative

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learning, from the results of the IPAS subject learning interviews using a collaborative approach. This collaborative use is carried out by teachers in IPAS teaching and learning activities to encourage the success of learning in the classroom gradually.

Identifying Needs

Identify needs in order to encourage collaborative learning to improve students' understanding of science learning. This includes identifying student needs, such as creating effective and relevant learning experiences, where students can work together to achieve shared learning goals. Collaborative learning, which involves interaction between students in groups to complete tasks together, is an effective strategy in this context. By identifying needs, teachers can design the right learning environment, such as providing relevant resources, determining appropriate learning strategies, and creating an atmosphere that supports cooperation between students. All of this aims to efficiently improve students' knowledge skills through a more fun and collaboration-based approach.

Group Formation

The stages of group formation in collaborative learning to improve students' understanding of science subjects for third grade students of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca include several structured stages, so that students can work together efficiently and all students are active in the learning process, the initial stage begins with the formation of student groups. The teacher divides the students into 4 groups, each group consists of 3 or 4 students. Small groups are created so that communication between students runs smoothly and each member can contribute. The formation of groups is carried out by placing able students in each group combined with students who are still less able, so that group defense runs effectively and trains students not to be picky about their friends.

Collaborative Activities

The stages of collaborative activities in a collaborative learning strategy in elementary school can be described as a series of steps designed to actively engage students in working together, sharing ideas, and solving tasks or problems in an integrated manner. The stages of collaborative activities in improving students' understanding of IPAS subjects with collaborative strategies include a series of steps that involve cooperation between students in the IPAS learning process. The purpose of using this collaborative learning is so that in groups, students can support each other and help each other, because differences in the level of ability of students in one group often result in significant variations in students' comprehension abilities. In one group, there are students who are less capable so that it is difficult to contribute, tend to ignore group assignments, and are more engrossed in playing alone. In this situation, the teacher only observes the way the students work and communicates and acts as a mentor when the student needs help. That way, students can strengthen their knowledge of the IPAS subjects that have been studied before. After students complete the assignment, they are asked to write the results of the group discussion on the board or read it in front of the class in turn.

Feedback Evaluation

Learning evaluation is a process to measure the extent to which learning goals can be achieved, as well as to provide feedback to students and teachers about the effectiveness of the learning process that has been implemented. In this observation, the evaluation of collaborative learning in improving students' comprehension skills was carried out by the teacher correcting the results of the students' discussions that he had read in front of the class, as well as giving praise to the group that had written correctly. Based on the results of interviews and observations that have been carried out, the implementation of collaborative learning strategies in third grade Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca is quite effective, because in the implementation of collaborative learning strategies can increase students' knowledge in the learning process, students' understanding of science subjects by using collaborative learning strategies is a fun thing for third grade students of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca. As for collaborative learning, there are also a number of limitations, we realize that the success of collaborative learning depends on a number of conditions. Kristiana and Ningsih (2017) The conditions include: 1. The results of the study show that a collaborative learning activity is said to be successful if the members do not just give simple responses about the task, but most importantly they must explain how they got the answers and why the answers are correct. 2. Each individual member of the group has responsibility for his or her group. 3. To create a group work or collaborative learning situation, each member needs to stay focused on the task, as the time spent completing the task is consistently related to the learning outcomes of the learners. 4. In each group, each member is interdependent. 5. A learning setting that encourages students to provide assistance to others and others receive such assistance allows for better interdependence. Collaborative learning refers to different types of teaching methods in which learners work in small teams, to support each other in understanding the subject. This allows learners to exchange ideas and provide feedback. (Buhun and friends, 2021) Collaborative learning is an educational process that involves

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students in a team to create knowledge and achieve learning goals collectively through social interaction under the direction of teachers both inside and outside the classroom, so that students will appreciate the contributions of all group members (Adawiyah & Jennah, 2023).

In the context of collaborative learning, a fun social atmosphere is created to support interactions that utilize students' diverse learning abilities and motivations. Small groups are organized in each class, which are made up of members with different characteristics such as gender, activity level, and cognitive capacity, thus allowing for a role of guidance and direction among the group members (Adawiyah & Jennah, 2023). Based on the previous data presentation, the application of collaborative learning strategies in this study shows that at the preparation stage, teachers first identify the characteristics of students, both in terms of academic ability, learning style, and social background. Teachers then form diverse learning groups, each of which consists of three to four students with different variations of abilities. The formation of this group is not done carelessly, but with consideration so that each group has members who can complement each other and collaborate. In addition, teachers also prepare worksheets and learning tools that are relevant to science and science materials, so that students can learn concretely and contextually.

In the implementation of the learning process, the classroom atmosphere becomes much more lively compared to conventional learning which was previously dominated by lectures. Students appear enthusiastic and active in discussing, exchanging ideas, and working together to complete the assigned group assignments. In the discussion process, the teacher plays the role of a facilitator who guides the course of the discussion, provides encouragement, and helps groups experiencing difficulties. The teacher also ensures that each member of the group has an equal opportunity to contribute, so that no student feels marginalized or just a follower. Through direct observation, it can be seen that students who previously tended to be passive began to dare to express their opinions and actively engage in group discussions. This shows that collaborative learning strategies are able to create an inclusive and participatory learning atmosphere, where every student feels valued and encouraged to develop their potential. Based on the results of the interview, students admitted that they prefer to study in groups because they can support each other and learn with their friends. Students find it easier to understand the social studies material if they discuss directly in groups, rather than just listening to explanations from the teacher. They also said the learning atmosphere became more fun and less boring. The teacher also revealed that with this method, students who were previously less confident began to show the courage to speak in front of the group and class. In addition, collaborative learning also encourages the development of social skills such as communication, tolerance, and shared responsibility. Teachers assess that interactions between students in groups can improve their ability to express opinions, listen to others, and resolve conflicts constructively.

The assessment of learning outcomes carried out through process and outcome evaluation shows progress in both conceptual understanding and students' critical thinking skills. Students can relate the IPAS material to the real experience around it. In addition, students also demonstrate collaborative skills in completing group assignments, such as compiling observation reports or presenting group results in front of the class. This increase in learning outcomes is not only seen from the grades obtained by students, but also from changes in their attitudes and behaviors during the learning process. Students become more active, creative, and responsible for the assignments given. Overall, the implementation of collaborative learning strategies in social studies subjects in third grade Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca is quite effective and has a positive influence on students' participation, concept understanding, and social skills. Learning becomes more meaningful because students are directly involved in the process of creating shared knowledge, in line with the learning objectives of social studies and the characteristics of 21st century education. These findings are in line with constructivist theories that emphasize the importance of social interaction in building understanding, and are supported by previous research showing that collaborative learning can improve students' learning outcomes and social skills.

CONCLUSION

From the research that has been conducted, the researcher concludes that the use of collaborative learning strategies in science subjects can have a positive impact on the learning process. The implementation of this strategy is able to increase students' activeness in doing assignments in groups, provide a deeper understanding for students, and can develop social skills and cooperation between students. By assigning tasks collaboratively and forming heterogeneous groups, by looking at the abilities and characteristics of students, collaborative implementation makes students become involved in discussions with friends, helps each other, and also makes students responsible for the results of their groups. However, in the implementation of collaborative, there are several challenges faced, such as the presence of students who are less active in the group, and the limited time students have to complete collaborative tasks. In addition, teachers are still limited in applying methods to the learning

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process, even though this collaborative learning strategy is very helpful in improving student learning outcomes in terms of material understanding, social skills, and positive attitudes towards science learning. Thus, collaborative learning strategies have proven to be effective in improving the quality of IPAS learning in grade three of Public Elementary Schools 1 Silanca.

Based on the above conclusions, here are some suggestions that can be given: 1. Teachers should continue to improve and implement collaborative learning strategies consistently in IPAS learning, so that students are used to working together and communicating efficiently with their peers, and teachers can learn more about strategies in the learning process so that they do not only use lecture methods, So that students do not feel bored in student learning and knowledge becomes more and more increasing. 2. Schools can provide training or workshops to teachers to deepen understanding and skills in implementing collaborative learning, so that the implementation in the classroom becomes more effective. 3. Students are expected to be actively involved in groups, respect each other's peers, and be responsible for the tasks given so that learning goals can be achieved properly. 4. Researchers can further expand this research by refining the subject and object of research, or exploring other factors that can affect the success of implementing collaborative learning strategies in elementary schools.

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